

Reproduction of paper results - Joint Geographical and Temporal Modeling Based on Matrix Factorization for Point-of-Interest Recommendation

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Abstract

The main goal of this paper is to reproduce the experimental setup, experiments, and results as explained in a paper by Rahmani et al. [1] from ECIR 2020 and to confirm the numbers and findings reported in the paper or, alternatively, uncover inconsistencies and therefore challenge the conclusions drawn. The paper chosen introduces a new algorithm for Point-of-Interest Recommendation. In the paper, several figures are included to show that the new algorithm is better in terms of precision, recall and nDCG(normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain). In the following paper, the goal is to reproduce these results. We also included all of our code, results and workflows on [github](#).

Keywords: Point-of-Interest Recommendation, reproducibility, experiment design, data science

1 Introduction

The paper by Rahmani et al. [1] investigates the performance of a new algorithm for Point-of-Interest Recommendation based on geospatial information called Spatio-Temporal Activity Center POI recommendation model, in the subsequent sections addressed as STACP. Even though many similar algorithms have been introduced, they argue that little research has been conducted on including not only temporal, but also spatial information in a POI recommendation system. The paper shows some figures to prove that their new algorithm is performing better than other algorithms which have already been used.

2 Datasets

The authors originally used two real-world check-in datasets from Gowalla and Foursquare provided in [2]. The Gowalla dataset consists of 620,683 world-wide check-ins made by 5,628 users on 31,803 POIs between February 2009 and October 2010. The Foursquare dataset includes 512,523 check-ins made by 7,642 users on 28,483 POIs in the United States from April 2012 to September 2013. Considering very long code running times and high similarity between the original results for both datasets, we decided to only use the Gowalla

dataset in our experiments. The dataset comes from a GitHub repository¹ provided in the original paper.

3 Evaluation Metrics

In the original paper three evaluation metrics were used: Precision@N, Recall@N and nDCG@N where $N \in \{10, 20\}$, standing for the top N recommendations considered for each user. In the reproduction process we decided to use the same metrics. Just like the authors, we used the earliest 70% check-ins as training data, the most recent 20% check-ins as test data and the remaining 10% as validation data.

4 Code

We used the Python code provided by the authors in a GitHub repository². As stated in the repository, in order to run it we had to create a virtual environment for Python 2.7 and reinstall all required packages. Later we also encountered some errors, mostly related to external .txt and .npy files. In order to mitigate these issues, we created two folders: result and tmp and also changed all file paths in the code accordingly so the respective files can be found. Another problem we encountered was extremely long running time of the code; each run took multiple hours. To mitigate this issue we tried only obtaining data necessary to reproduce the results of the original paper. For example, we didn't calculate the evaluation metrics for $N \in \{5, 15\}$ and partially omitted the MAP@N metric (all of which was present and to be executed in the original file from GitHub). All these actions reduced the running time barely noticeably, which is why in all the experiments we tried to run the code as few times as possible. Another unexpected issue we encountered was that the code provided by the authors focused only on their original STACP algorithm, omitting implementation of other, state-of-the-art POI recommendation approaches used for comparisons. After some research, we found an implementation of one of those algorithms online³: LRT, which we later used to compare with three variants of the STACP approach. The underlying logic behind this decision is that implementing all the baseline algorithms mentioned in the original paper

¹<https://github.com/rahmanidashti/STACP>

²<https://github.com/rahmanidashti/STACP>

³<http://spatialkeyword.sce.ntu.edu.sg/eval-vldb17/>

Table 1. Reproduced performance comparison in terms of Precision@N, Recall@N, and nDCG@N for $N \in \{10, 20\}$ on Gowalla.

	Precision		Recall		nDCG	
	@10	@20	@10	@20	@10	@20
LRT	0.0248	0.0195	0.0214	0.0326	0.0194	0.0174
STACP -NoCTX	0.0281	0.0199	0.1923	0.0305	0.0183	0.0184
STACP -NoTC	0.0283	0.0277	0.0282	0.0368	0.0279	0.0250
STACP	0.0384	0.0326	0.0405	0.0667	0.0409	0.0364

would take too much effort compared to its potential gain since the paper mostly focused on the STACP algorithm. On the other hand, juxtaposing the STACP with LRT allowed us to prove that the metrics for this baseline algorithm was accurate and to prove the superiority of the STACP over the LRT method.

5 Reproduced Results

5.1 Performance Evaluation Against Compared Methods.

Table 1 shows the comparison between the reproduced performance of the three variants of the STACP algorithm and a baseline LRT algorithm. The numbers obtained are similar to the data from the original paper. The goal of the original paper was to check if the metrics for the STACP algorithm are significantly higher than the metrics for the state-of-the-art approaches and other variants of the STACP. It was mentioned that two-tailed paired t-tests at a 95% confidence interval ($p < 0.05$) were conducted. However, the actual p-values were not included. Therefore we calculated them and they are shown in table 2. All of the values are, indeed, lower than 0.05. However, we did stumble upon what we think might be a conclusion flaw. Namely, in tables 1 and 2 the recall@10 for STACP-NoCTX are in bold font, since this metric was significantly higher for the NoCTX variant than for regular STACP. And so, the p-value is below 0.05 but the authors claimed that the STACP outperforms its NoCTX variant, whereas in fact that is not true. We were also curious why the value of this metric differs so much from similar metrics but unfortunately could not find a satisfying answer. We did however obtain a very similar reproduction result which proves it was accurate in the original paper and not for example a typo. Despite this minor flaw, the reproduced experiments proved that the STACP outperforms both the suggested baseline method LRT and its two inferior variants significantly.

Table 2. P-values of a two-tailed paired t-test of the reproduced results compared with the STACP algorithm.

	Precision		Recall		nDCG	
	@10	@20	@10	@20	@10	@20
LRT	2e-29	5e-50	1e-41	1e-70	2e-69	3e-86
STACP -NoCTX	2e-19	4e-47	1e-244	1e-87	3e-83	2e-85
STACP -NoTC	9e-19	1e-07	8e-18	1e-55	1e-25	2e-30

Figure 1. Comparison of original nDCG and reproduced nDCG and mAP calculations

5.2 Possible confusion in the paper

Comparing our results to the values stated in the paper, we get very similar results for precision and recall, as mentioned in the upper section. However, nDCG (normalised Discounted Cumulative Gain) is not similar at all, showing that the values calculated by us are more than 70% higher compared to the original data. After some investigation, we found out that the nDCG value shown in the paper is very different to our nDCG value, but very similar to our mAP (mean average Precision) value. Without further proof, we therefore want to mention the possibility that those two metrics were confused in the paper. This investigation also holds when comparing nDCGs for different Percentages of POIs visited by users. Figure 1 shows the comparison between the nDCG value in the paper, the nDCG value and mAP value found when we ran the experiment. Table 3 also shows a comparison of the actual values stated in the paper and the ones reproduced for top 10 and top 20 recommendations. Unfortunately, mAP was not stated in the original paper. Therefore, we cannot confirm our theory given the data at hand.

Table 3. Comparison of nDCG and mAP

	nDCG		mAP	
	@10	@20	@10	@20
original	0.0212	0.0211	-	-
reproduced	0.0409	0.036401	0.021783	0.021671

5.3 Effect of Activity Centers.

To reproduce this experiment, temporal states were removed from the implementation of the STACP algorithm by changing the value of Lambda to 1.0, hence only considering the whole matrix and not splitting the data in work time and leisure time. The values obtained from this model proved to be similar to the values from the original paper (see tables 1, 2). The STACP outperformed its NoTC variant in terms of all employed metrics. These results support the authors’ hypothesis that users’ POIs of choice depend on their temporal state.

5.4 Effect of Contextual Model.

To create result files for the STACP-NoCTX model we adjusted the model equation in the recommendation.py file as described in the original paper. The obtained results shown in tables 1 and 2 prove that the use of Contextual Model leads to improving performance in all metrics with the exception of the already mentioned recall@10. This shows that the authors were right suggesting that using contextual information enables STACP to model the users’ behavior more accurately and that by incorporating the contextual information, one can address the data sparsity problem.

5.5 Effect of Number of Visited POIs per user.

To study the effect of the number of visited POIs per user, Rahmani et al. [1] have evaluated the performance of the STACP algorithm on different data sizes. Therefore, the original training data set was reduced to only a certain percentage of random POIs visited by each user. To reproduce the results, we have transformed the original training data set to include for each user only parts of the POIs visited. To do so, we generated a random sample for each user only containing N % of POIs visited by each user, where $N \in \{40,60,80,100\}$. Based on these training sets, the STACP algorithm was run on each data set and the performance metrics were then calculated based on the recommendations produced by the algorithm. As for the experiments above, we reduced the analysis to include the three versions of the STACP algorithm (No Context, No Temporal information and full model) and the LRT algorithm as a reference model.

As shown in figure 2, the full STACP model (shown in blue) is very robust to sparse data, whereas the reference model experiences a huge drop if a certain threshold of data sparsity is reached, nDCG performance sinking by over 70%

Figure 2. Performance comparison of different sparsity levels**Table 4.** Performance comparison of different sparsity levels for top 20 recommendations in terms of Precision, Recall, nDCG and mAP

	Precision	Recall	nDCG	mAP
STACP 40%	0.026457	0.053464	0.028952	0.015974
STACP 60%	0.028483	0.058430	0.031180	0.017743
STACP 80%	0.030792	0.062946	0.034059	0.019537
STACP 100%	0.032578	0.066694	0.036401	0.021671

when comparing the model performance of training data containing 60% of the full data to the 40% model. Hence, the conclusion of the authors [1] can be confirmed that the full STACP algorithm is more robust to data sparsity than the reference algorithm LRT. Furthermore, it is also well visible in figure 2 that the combination of temporal and spatial information contributes to the robustness of the full model as performance drops rapidly when only considering temporal information (shown in green).

Table 4 shows a comparison of the performance measures for the full STACP model on various sparsity levels. We can see that performance drops with a lower amount of data, as we would expect. Interestingly, all performances are significantly better (using a two-sample T-test) than those of any reduced STACP model, like only using time components or only using context to train the model.

5.6 Effect of Model Parameters.

Figures 3-5 show the performance of STACP for different value of d, alpha and lambda. It can be seen that the optimal value of d is 15. This parameter result shows that there is tendency to visit close POIs that create regions. Optimal

Figure 3. Effect on precision and recall of parameter d.

Figure 4. Effect on precision and recall of parameter alpha.

value of alpha is 0.02. This parameter is a threshold for when an area is considered as its own region. The optimum value for lambda is 0.5 for precision and recall, which shows that users tend to spend their time in different areas depending on their temporal state as lambda is used as a parameter for weighting leisure and work time. When we set this parameter to 1 (just working time) or 0 (just leisure time), the performance decreases.

6 Additional Testing

We also decided to perform some additional tests on the Gowalla data set to check its suitability for testing the algorithm. If the data set is biased in only including check-in locations with a high amount of total check-ins, the data might not be accurate. Figures 6 and 7 show that after filtering out locations with amount of check-ins smaller than 10, most locations have a small amount of check-ins. This fact suggests that variation of locations is big so there should be a reasonably high variation in check-ins in our data set.

If there is a lot of users that are checked-in only few times we may suspect that the data set is not very accurate. Using the same method as above, we can find how many users in our data set are recorded to have a small amount of total check-ins. The bigger amount of check-ins the more accurate conclusions we can draw from the data. In figures 8 and 9 we can clearly see that virtually all of the users have at least 10 check-ins, compared to only half of the locations having more than 10 check-ins. To find out how many users in the data set attend a big amount of different places we calculated a ratio of sum of all check-ins to sum of unique places for

Figure 5. Effect on precision and recall of parameter lambda.

each user (figure 10). As we can see, most of the users attend a small amount of different places.

7 Conclusion

Overall, despite the article looking fairly easily reproducible at first sight with both code and data sets provided, it proved to be a hard task. The code was not complete (only the STACP

Figure 6. Amount of total check-ins in given location.

Figure 7. Amount of total check-ins in given location for locations visited >10 times.

Figure 8. Amount of total check-ins of users.

Figure 9. Amount of total check-ins for users with >10 check-ins.

Figure 10. Sum of all check-ins / sum of different locations

algorithm included), did not run out-of-the-box and the running time was enormously long. Eventually however we managed to reproduce all the experiments conducted in the original paper and were able to confirm most of the conclusions drawn in it. We also found two experiment flaws, namely a possible mix-up of nDCG and mAP measures and a confusion, where the reduced model seems to be better-performing than the full model. However, they did not influence the overall conclusions. Additionally we conducted some extra statistical test to explore the given Gowalla dataset and proved its usefulness. In further research, the flaw regarding the nDCG and mAP metrics, as well as unreasonably high recall@10 value for the STACP-NoCTX algorithm could be explored. We would also suggest analyzing the impact of the amount of check-ins for locations and users in a dataset on the model accuracy.

8 Appendix

code for reproduction: <https://github.com/Kat-rin-sc/EDDS-Project>

References

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